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Involvement Of Non-Catholic Students in The Catholic School Environment

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to assess the involvement of non-Catholic students in the Catholic school environment. Adopting a quantitative approach, descriptive design, and survey method, the study was conducted at Saint Paul University Surigao with 106 selected non-Catholic senior high school students. The findings revealed that most of the participants were female, with Grade 12 students being the majority. Regarding religious affiliation, the largest group belonged to the United Church of Christ in the Philippines (UUCP). The involvement of non-Catholic students in the school environment was highest in the social and pedagogical aspects, followed by spiritual engagement. No significant difference in involvement was found based on sex, religious affiliation, or academic strand. However, psychological involvement differed significantly between Grade 11 and Grade 12 students, with Grade 12 students reporting higher levels of psychological support. The study emphasizes the need for inclusive practices in curriculum development and enhancing support for non-Catholic students in psychological and spiritual areas.

Keywords: *Non-Catholic students, Catholic school environment, involvement, pedagogical, social, psychological, spiritual.*

I. Introduction

In educational systems worldwide, Catholic schools play a significant role in providing academic instruction intertwined with moral and religious education. These institutions uphold a distinct set of teachings, values, and traditions rooted in the Catholic faith. While Catholic schools are deeply committed to faith-based education, they also welcome students from diverse backgrounds, including those of non-Catholic beliefs. This integration of faith with learning is a

longstanding tradition that has made Catholic schools attractive to students from various religious backgrounds, including those who do not identify with the Catholic faith (Bolton, 2023).

The decision for non-Catholic families to enroll their children in Catholic schools may stem from several factors, such as the school's academic reputation, discipline standards, or a desire for a values-based education. However, this choice can also introduce unique dynamics, including ideological disagreements, identity issues, and feelings of loneliness, which can lead to exclusion. As non-Catholic students navigate a religiously oriented environment that may not align with their personal beliefs and backgrounds, they may experience significant difficulties. Although they may initially be unfamiliar with Catholic practices and teachings, some students still find comfort and peace in the environment provided by Catholic schools (Klemond, 2023). Furthermore, non-Catholic parents often choose Catholic schools because they perceive these institutions as places that respect students and emphasize learning and moral values (Genevieve, 2019).

Nevertheless, observations at St. Paul University Surigao indicate that non-Catholic students face significant challenges in participating in Catholic activities. These students often experience disagreements or exclusion due to their religious differences, which can negatively impact their sense of belonging and overall well-being. Consequently, feelings of exclusion or disrespect based on religious differences can adversely affect their mental health, social interactions, and academic experiences. According to Kumar et al. (2023), religious diversity in schools can lead to positive outcomes, such as increased tolerance, empathy, and understanding among students from different religious backgrounds. However, when students face discrimination or exclusion based on their religious beliefs, it can have detrimental effects on their emotional well-being and sense of belonging within the school community. Additionally, a study conducted by the National Association of School Psychologists (NASP, 2019) found that students who experience religious discrimination or bullying may suffer from increased stress, anxiety, and feelings of isolation.

While existing research emphasizes the potential for positive outcomes in religiously diverse school environments—such as increased tolerance, empathy, and understanding (Kumar et al., 2023; Banks, 2015)—there remains a notable gap in studies specifically focusing on the exclusion and discrimination non-Catholic students experience during Catholic religious activities, such as prayers or school Masses. Most studies tend to address general issues of religious diversity in schools but overlook the unique emotional and social challenges non-Catholic students face when engaging in religious practices they are unfamiliar with or do not personally follow. For instance, during communal religious practices like prayer, non-Catholic students may struggle to participate or express themselves in a way that feels authentic to their beliefs. As a result, this sense of exclusion can lead to heightened feelings of isolation,

discomfort, and even anxiety, all of which negatively impact their overall well-being and sense of belonging within the school community.

This study seeks to address this gap by exploring the specific experiences of non-Catholic students who face exclusion, disrespect, or discomfort during Catholic religious activities. Understanding these experiences is essential for highlighting the emotional and social challenges these students encounter, which may hinder their ability to fully participate in both the academic and social aspects of their school life. Furthermore, the significance of this research lies in its potential to promote a deeper understanding of how non-Catholic students navigate their identities within a Catholic educational setting. By exploring how instances of discrimination or exclusion affect their mental health and self-expression, this study aims to contribute to creating a more inclusive and supportive environment for all students.

II. Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine the Involvement of Non-Catholic Students in the Catholic School Environment, which specifically answers the following research problems;

1. What is the profile of the participants in terms of:
 - 1.1. Sex;
 - 1.2. Grade Level;
 - 1.3. strand; and
 - 1.4. Religious Affiliation?
2. What is the Involvement of Non-Catholic Student in the Catholic School Environment in terms of:
 - 2.1. Pedagogical;
 - 2.2. Social;
 - 2.3. Psychological;
 - 2.4. Cultural; and
 - 2.5. Spiritual?
3. Is there a significant difference between the Involvement of Non-Catholic Student in the Catholic School Environment when grouped according to the profile variable?
4. What recommendations may be proposed for the study?

III. Hypothesis

At 0.05 level of significance, it is hypothesized that there is no significant difference between the Involvement of Non-Catholic Student in the Catholic School Environment when grouped according to the profile variable?

IV. Methodology

This study utilized a quantitative approach, employing the purposive sampling. The chosen research design was deemed appropriate because the study seeks to attain more excellent knowledge and understanding regarding the involvement of non-Catholic students in the Catholic school environment, such as pedagogical, social, psychological, cultural, and spiritual. This research only included the identified 106 selected non-Catholic students from senior high school grades 11 and 12, enrolled in the academic strands of Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM), Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS), Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM), Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL), and Arts and Design (ADT) at Saint Paul University Surigao using a purposive sampling. The questionnaires were then disseminated to the 106 participants who agreed to take part in the study. After the participants completed the questionnaires, the researchers retrieved, tallied, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted the data.

V. Results and Discussions

This chapter presents the result and discussion of the data. The data presented follows the order of the problems cited in the problem statement; profile of the participants, involvement of Non-Catholic Students in the Catholic School Environment, and significant difference in the involvement of non-Catholic, students in the catholic school environment as to profile.

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents

Profile	f (106)	%
Sex		
Female	64	60
Male	42	40
Grade Level		
Grade 12	58	55
Grade 11	48	45
Religious Affiliations		
Baptist	6	6
Born Again Christian	17	16
Christian	1	1
Church the Body of Christ	1	1
FGGCC	1	1
Free Methodist	2	2
Grace Gospel Church of Christ	2	2
IFI	28	26
INC	3	3
Islam	3	3

Jehovas Witnesses	1	1
MCGI	2	2
Pentecostal	3	3
Seventh-Day Adventist	7	6
UCCP	29	27
Strand		
ABM	23	22
HUMSS	18	17
STEM	57	53
TVL/ADT	8	8

Table 1 presents the profile of the selected 106 Non-Catholics Students in the Catholic School Environment regarding of their sex, grade level, religious affiliation, and strand.

Among the participants, the majority are female, comprising of 64 individuals (60%), while 42 individuals (40%) are male. Most participants are in Grade 12, totaling of 58 individuals (55%), while the remaining 48 individuals (45%) are in Grade 11. Regarding religious affiliation, the largest group belongs to Iglesia Filipina Independiente (IFI), with 28 individuals (26%), followed by United Church of Christ in the Philippines (UCCP) (29 individuals, 27%), Born Again Christians (17 individuals, 16%), Iglesia Ni Cristo (INC) (3 individuals, 3%), Islam (3 individuals, 3%), Pentecostal (3 individuals, 3%), Seventh-Day Adventist (7 individuals, 6%), Baptist (6 individuals, 6%), MCGI (2 individuals, 2%), Free Methodist (2 individuals, 2%), Grace Gospel Church of Christ (2 individuals, 2%), Jehovah's Witnesses (1 individual, 1%), Church the Body of Christ (1 individual, 1%), Christian (1 individual, 1%), FGGCC (1 individual, 1%). In terms of academic strands, most participants belong to STEM (57 individuals, 53%), followed by ABM (23 individuals, 22%), HUMSS (18 individuals, 17%), and lastly TVL/ADT (8 individuals, 8%).

Table 2.1 *The Involvement of Non-Catholic Students in the Catholic School Environment in terms of pedagogical.*

Indicators	M	SD	VR	I
A1. I feel that the teaching methods in the school are inclusive and cater to the diverse needs of all students,	2.82	0.86	A	GE
A2. The curriculum reflects a balanced perspective that respects and incorporates a variety of religious and cultural view-points.	2.90	0.88	A	GE
A3. Teachers provide an open and supportive environment where I can express my thoughts and opinions freely.	3.08	0.95	A	GE
A4. I feel that my learning experience is valued and	3.00	0.95	A	GE

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respected, regardless of my religious or cultural background.

A5. The school’s teaching practices foster an environment of mutual respects and understanding between students of different faiths and backgrounds.

Scale	Interval	Verbal Response	Qualitative Interpretation
4	3.25 – 4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very Great Extent (VCE)
3	2.50 – 3.24	Agree (A)	Great Extent (GE)
2	1.75 – 2.49	Disagree (D)	Moderate Extent (ME)
1	1.00 – 1.74	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Low Extent (LE)

Table 2.1 displays the involvement of Non-Catholic Students in the catholic school environment regarding pedagogical.

Among the five indicators, the highest-rated statement, *"Teachers provide an open and supportive environment where I can express my thoughts and opinions freely"* (mean score of 3.08), highlights the positive perception of non-Catholic students about their teachers' approach. This transmits that Catholic schools, despite their religious foundation, have succeeded in creating an environment where students, regardless of their religious background, feel comfortable and supported in expressing their ideas. This outcome aligns with the idea that Catholic schools aim to provide a holistic education that nurtures both intellectual growth and moral development. The concept of freedom and charity, as reflected in the Gospel spirit, is often linked with creating an atmosphere of acceptance and mutual respect. Caridi (2021) points out that the educational philosophy of Catholic schools emphasizes creating such a welcoming and supportive environment, which could explain why students perceive their teachers as open and receptive.

Furthermore, Catholic schools are well-regarded for their high academic standards, and this likely extends to their fostering of an inclusive learning environment. Also, the fact that non-Catholic students feel encouraged to share their thoughts aligns with Klemond (2023) and Pohlen (2023), who observe that Catholic schools have historically provided an environment where students, regardless of faith, are welcomed. Besides, the emphasis on academic rigor and a supportive learning climate likely reinforces these positive perceptions. In contrast, the lowest-rated statement, *"I feel that the teaching methods in the school are inclusive and cater to the diverse needs of all students"* (mean score of 2.82), signals some concerns about how well the school’s teaching methods address the needs of non-Catholic students. While the mean score still indicates general agreement, the relatively lower rating suggests that students perceive limitations in the inclusivity of teaching strategies. The matter of inclusivity in teaching methods may arise from the fact that Catholic schools prioritize religious education as a central element of their curriculum, which can influence teaching approaches. As noted by White (2023), Catholic schools may have a curriculum and teaching methodologies that are particularly shaped by religious content and values. This focus on religious education might

unintentionally limit the ability of teaching methods to be as flexible and inclusive for students from diverse religious and cultural backgrounds.

The assessment also touches on the connection between grade level and the perception of inclusivity. The psychological indicators put in mind that as student's progress to higher grade levels, they may become more aware of instructional limitations, such as a lack of inclusivity in teaching methods. Older students may have developed a clearer understanding of their educational needs and may be more attuned to how well the school meets those needs. This imply to the rise of inclusivity in teaching methods that might become more pronounced for older non-Catholic students who have had more time to reflect on their educational experience. Their higher ratings of non-inclusivity could be related to their developing sense of self-identity and greater awareness of how their religious background may make them feel distanced from certain aspects of the curriculum. Older students are also more likely to have encountered a wider variety of teaching styles, which may increase their expectations for a more adaptable pedagogical approach.

In effect, the concern of psychological distance is notable. As Catholic schools emphasize faith-based education, non-Catholic students may sometimes feel a sense of otherness or social identity conflict, which affects their perceptions of the pedagogical environment. Therefore, the stronger religious identity within Catholic schools may subtly impact the sense of belonging for non-Catholic students. As the feeling of not fully integrating into the faith-based aspects of the curriculum may contribute to their perception that the teaching methods are not fully inclusive. These psychological factors, including belongingness and the alignment (or lack thereof) between their own social identity and the identity promoted by the school, could lead non-Catholic students to perceive a gap between their learning needs and what is being provided.

Despite these concerns, the overall average score of 2.95 for the five pedagogical indicators convey that non-Catholic student's, on the whole, do perceive the Catholic school environment as inclusive to a large extent. While there are areas for enhancement—particularly in how teaching methods can be more inclusive and responsive to diverse needs—the overall impression remains positive. In summary, non-Catholic students in Catholic schools generally feel supported by their teachers and find the school environment open and conducive to free expression. However, they express some reservations about how well the teaching methods cater to their diverse needs, with older students in particular more aware of these limitations.

Table 2.2 *The Involvement of Non-Catholic Students in the Catholic School Environment in terms of social.*

Indicators	M	SD	VR	I
B1. I feel accepted and valued by my peers in the school.	3.08	0.98	A	GE
B2. I have positive social interaction and friendship with my fellow Catholic Students.	3.18	0.94	A	GE
B3. The school inclusivity, ensuring that I feel part of social groups and school activities.	3.05	0.81	A	GE
B4. I feel that I can engage in school events and	2.97	0.95	A	GE

activities without being excluded.

B5. The school promotes an environment where students from diverse religions and cultural backgrounds can interact and collaborate respectfully. 2.91 0.97 A GE

	Average			
	3.04	0.93	A	GE
Scale	Interval	Verbal Response	Qualitative Interpretation	
4	3.25 – 4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very Great Extent (VCE)	
3	2.50 – 3.24	Agree (A)	Great Extent (GE)	
2	1.75 – 2.49	Disagree (D)	Moderate Extent (ME)	
1	1.00 – 1.74	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Low Extent (LE)	

Table 2.2 display the Involvement of Non-Catholic Students in the Catholic School Environment regarding social.

Among the five indicators, the highest-rated statement, *"I have positive social interaction and friendship with my fellow Catholic students"* (M = 3.18), highlights the strong peer relationships experienced by non-Catholic students within the Catholic school environment. This means that Catholic schools, despite their religious foundation, have successfully fostered a welcoming atmosphere where students, regardless of their religious background, feel accepted and able to form meaningful friendships. The positive rating on this indicator reflects how interpersonal relationships play a vital role in creating an inclusive school culture.

This outcome aligns with the broader goal of Catholic education, which emphasizes values such as respect, kindness, and community. Catholic schools often encourage students to build relationships based on mutual understanding and cooperation, reinforcing a sense of belonging among all students. Imcara (2021) highlights that Catholic schools integrate these values into their educational framework, ensuring that non-Catholic students also feel included. Additionally, Hudson et al. (2021) emphasize the significance of peer relationships in students' social and emotional development, noting that friendships contribute to overall well-being and academic success. Given the school's commitment to fostering a strong sense of community, it is unsurprising that non-Catholic students report positive social interactions with their Catholic peers.

In contrast, the lowest-rated statement, *"The school promotes an environment where students from diverse religions and cultural backgrounds can interact and collaborate respectfully"* (M = 2.91), inferring some concerns regarding institutional inclusivity. While the score still indicates a generally positive perception, it is the lowest among the five indicators, suggesting that structured efforts to promote inclusivity could be further developed. Although interpersonal relationships among students are strong, institutional initiatives aimed at fostering interfaith due and cultural exchange may require enhancement. Mikhael et al. (2020) stress the importance of structured programs that encourage respect and collaboration among students from diverse religious backgrounds. Likewise, the First Asian Bishops Conference (FABC) Plenary Assembly underscores the need for interreligious dialogue, particularly in the areas of

engagement with marginalized communities, cultural exchanges, and discussions on religious diversity.

Moreover, as researchers observed that while many non-Catholic students experience positive peer interactions, some still face subtle forms of exclusion, difficulties in fully participating in religious activities, and occasional instances of bullying. In consequence, these experiences can create barriers to full integration within the school community. Therefore, feelings of exclusion, whether explicit or implicit, may affect students' overall sense of belonging, which in turn can impact their academic motivation and well-being, especially when non-Catholic students feel that their religious identity is not fully acknowledged or respected within the broader school culture, it may lead to a sense of social distance from the institution (Eisenberg et al., 2017; Banks, 2015).

In connection with that, the assessment also reveals a connection between grade level and the perception of inclusivity. Just as psychological indicators has shows that as student’s progress to a higher grade levels, they may become more aware of social and institutional barriers to inclusivity. Thus, the data indicate that the psychological aspect significantly rejects the null hypothesis ($p = 0.029$), implying that grade level plays a crucial role in shaping students’ experiences. For instance: older students, having spent more time in the school environment, may develop a greater sensitivity to exclusionary behaviors and institutional practices that may not fully support religious diversity. And may also experience increased pressure to conform to the dominant religious culture, which can lead to feelings of isolation or discomfort.

Additionally, these psychological factors, particularly the sense of belonging and identity alignment within the school, contribute to students’ perceptions of inclusivity. As Catholic schools emphasize faith-based education, non-Catholic students may sometimes experience a sense of otherness, which affects their engagement with the school’s cultural and religious aspects.

Despite these concerns, the overall average score of 3.04 for the five social indicators suggests that non-Catholic students, on the whole, perceive their social experiences in Catholic schools as largely positive. While areas for refinement exist—particularly in strengthening interfaith initiatives and promoting institutional inclusivity—the overall impression remains favorable.

Table 2.3 *The Involvement of Non-Catholic Students in the Catholic School Environment in terms of psychological*

Indicators	M	SD	VR	I
C1. I feel psychologically safe and supported in the school, regardless of my religious backgrounds.	3.01	0.88	A	GE
C2. The school foster an atmosphere of respect and understanding that helps me feel emotionally secure.	2.99	0.83	A	GE
C3. I feel comfortable discussing my personal belief and experiences without a fear of judgement or discrimination.	2.90	0.87	A	GE
C4. The school’s policies and practices create a	2.89	0.84	A	GE

psychologically inclusive environment where students of different faiths and cultures feel valued.

C5. I experienced a sense of belonging in the school community, even though the majority of students are Catholic. 3.01 0.95 A GE

	Average			
	2.96	0.88	A	GE
Scale	Interval	Verbal Response	Qualitative Interpretation	
4	3.25 – 4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very Great Extent (VCE)	
3	2.50 – 3.24	Agree (A)	Great Extent (GE)	
2	1.75 – 2.49	Disagree (D)	Moderate Extent (ME)	
1	1.00 – 1.74	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Low Extent (LE)	

Table 2.3 displays the involvement of non-Catholic students in the Catholic School Environment regarding psychological.

Among the five indicators, the highest-rated statements, *"I feel psychologically safe and supported in the school, regardless of my religious background"* and *"I experienced a sense of belonging in the school community, even though the majority of students are Catholic"* (both with a mean score of 3.01), highlight the positive perception of non-Catholic students regarding their psychological well-being in the school. These findings means that Catholic schools, despite their religious foundation, have successfully created an environment where students of different faiths feel safe, included, and supported. This result aligns with the broader goal of Catholic schools to foster a welcoming and holistic educational experience that nurtures not only academic excellence but also emotional and moral development. The emphasis on respect and inclusivity, rooted in Catholic teachings, contributes to this atmosphere of belonging. According to Mayhew and Rockenbach (2021), schools that prioritize interfaith dialogue and mutual respect help students feel psychologically secure, even in religiously homogenous settings. Similarly, Kowalski (2023) discusses how Catholic schools have historically provided spaces where students from various backgrounds feel valued, which likely reinforces the perception of safety and belonging among non-Catholic students.

However, despite the overall positive perception, some matters remain. The lowest-rated statement, *"The school's policies and practices create a psychologically inclusive environment where students of different faiths and cultures feel valued"* (M = 2.89), shows that while students generally feel included, there is still room for institutional efforts to further validate and recognize diverse religious identities. Similarly, the statement *"I feel comfortable discussing my personal beliefs and experiences without a fear of judgment or discrimination"* (M = 2.90) indicates that while open discussions are encouraged, some students may still hesitate to fully express their religious perspectives. This aligns with Goldberg's (2023) optimal distinctiveness theory, which suggests that when institutions focus too heavily on commonalities between religious groups, minority students may struggle with maintaining their unique identity. Consequently, this can lead to feelings of being overlooked rather than fully integrated into the school community. Additionally, Kaufman (2020) notes that students in faith-based schools may face challenges in

reconciling their personal beliefs with the dominant religious identity of the institution, which may explain why some non-Catholic students feel that their faith is not always fully acknowledged.

Furthermore, the assessment highlights a connection between grade level and the perception of psychological safety. The statistical analysis reveals that psychological factors significantly vary by grade level ($t = -2.212, p = 0.029$), indicating that as students progress academically, their perceptions of psychological support evolve. Older students, in particular, may become more aware of how religious identity influences school policies and classroom discussions. Kaufman (2020) argues that as students develop a stronger sense of self-identity, they may become more attuned to aspects of their environment that either support or challenge their religious background. Additionally, Mayhew and Rockenbach (2021) emphasize that as students advance in their educational journey, their expectations for inclusivity and open dialogue may increase. Consequently, they may become more critical of areas where they feel their religious identity is not fully recognized.

Despite these concerns, the overall average mean score of 2.96 suggests that non-Catholic students generally perceive the school environment as psychologically supportive to a “Great Extent”. While institutional policies and opportunities for open discussions can further strengthen this inclusivity, the overall sentiment remains positive, reflecting the school’s commitment to fostering a psychologically safe and accepting atmosphere.

Table 2.4 *The Involvement of Non-Catholic Students in the Catholic School Environment in terms of cultural.*

Indicator		M	SD	VR	I
D1. I feel my school curriculum acknowledge and respects the cultural diversity of Non-Catholic students,		2.91	0.86	A	GE
D2. I think that my school successfully minimize cultural and religious segregation among students.		2.94	0.85	A	GE
D3. I believe that the values of integrity and respects, as taught in my school, are essential for building a harmonious community.		3.04	0.89	A	GE
D4. I feel that Non-Catholic students have opportunity to participate to participate in school traditions and events without feeling excluded.		2.95	0.96	A	GE
D5. I believe that learning about different cultures and religions contributes positively to my educational experience.		3.07	0.91	A	GE
Average		2.98	0.89	A	GE
Scale	Interval	Verbal Response		Qualitative Interpretation	
4	3.25 – 4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)		Very Great Extent (VCE)	
3	2.50 – 3.24	Agree (A)		Great Extent (GE)	

2	1.75 – 2.49	Disagree (D)	Moderate Extent (ME)
1	1.00 – 1.74	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Low Extent (LE)

Table 2.4 displays the involvement of non-Catholic students in the Catholic school environments regarding cultural.

Among the five indicators, the highest-rated statement, *"I believe that learning about different cultures and religions contributes positively to my educational experience"* (mean score of 3.07), highlights the positive perception of non-Catholic students regarding the role of cultural diversity in their education. Clearly, Catholic schools provide meaningful opportunities for students to engage with diverse cultural and religious perspectives, fostering a well-rounded educational experience.

This finding aligns with the research of Frexia and Aneas (2020), who emphasize that inclusive education should actively minimize cultural and religious segregation. By incorporating diverse cultural teachings, Catholic schools uphold their mission of providing holistic education, as discussed by Caridi (2021). Furthermore, the integration of cultural awareness within the curriculum fosters a sense of appreciation among non-Catholic students, reinforcing the idea that Catholic schools aim to nurture both intellectual and moral development. In addition, the emphasis on diversity supports Speas' (2020) assertion that fairness, respect, and kindness are crucial in maintaining a harmonious learning environment. As a result, the perception of inclusivity in cultural learning reflects the success of Catholic schools in cultivating an atmosphere of mutual respect and understanding, benefiting students of all backgrounds.

On the other hand, the lowest-rated statement, *"I think that my school successfully minimizes cultural and religious segregation among students"* (mean score of 2.94), reveals that while non-Catholic students recognize the value of cultural learning, some still perceive a level of segregation within the school environment. Although the mean score indicates general agreement, the lower rating implies that religious or cultural differences remain noticeable in social interactions or institutional structures. Consequently, some students may feel that full integration has not yet been achieved.

Moreover, the psychological indicators further reveal that perceptions of cultural segregation may be influenced by grade level. Specifically, the data shows that psychological factors related to grade level were statistically significant (-2.212, $p = 0.029$), indicating that as student's progress, they become more aware of social and cultural dynamics within the school. In particular, older students may develop a heightened awareness of inclusivity issues, leading to a more critical perspective on how well the school integrates non-Catholic students. These exposure align with White (2023), who argues that the faith-based structure of Catholic schools can create subtle social divisions, particularly for students who do not share the dominant religious beliefs.

In addition to grade level, the sense of cultural segregation may also be linked to psychological factors such as belongingness and identity. As discussed by Hillman (2024), students from different religious backgrounds may feel a degree of separation when exposed to school traditions and religious activities that do not align with their personal beliefs. While Catholic schools strive for inclusivity, their inherent religious framework may still create a sense of

"otherness" for some non-Catholic students. This sense of detachment could explain why the perception of minimized segregation received the lowest rating.

Nevertheless, despite these concerns, the overall average score of 2.98 for cultural indicators reflects a generally positive experience for non-Catholic students in Catholic schools. While some students feel that cultural and religious segregation still exists, the strong emphasis on cultural learning and diversity helps mitigate these concerns.

In conclusion, non-Catholic students in Catholic schools recognize the positive impact of learning about different cultures and religions on their education. However, as they advance through grade levels, some become more aware of cultural and religious segregation, highlighting the ongoing need for efforts to promote inclusivity. Moving forward, strengthening inclusive teaching strategies and fostering cross-cultural interactions could further enhance the sense of belonging among non-Catholic students.

Table 2.5 *The Involvement of non-Catholic Students in the Catholic School Environment in terms of spiritual*

Indicator	M	SD	VR	I
E1. I feel comfortable participating in the school's spiritual or religious activities like Mass, Marian Camp, Living Rosary, and the like.	2.94	0.94	A	GE
E2. I feel that the spiritual teachings in the school are presented in a way that is respectful to all students.	3.12	0.89	A	GE
E3. I am encouraged to share and express my Spiritual or religious perspective during class discussion.	2.86	0.91	A	GE
E4. I feel an inclusive spiritual environment where my faith is respected and valued.	3.11	0.92	A	GE
E5. I feel that my spiritual beliefs are respected in the Catholic school daily practices and interactions.	3.08	0.88	A	GE
Average	3.02	0.91	A	GE

Scale	Interval	Verbal Response	Qualitative Interpretation
4	3.25 – 4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very Great Extent (VCE)
3	2.50 – 3.24	Agree (A)	Great Extent (GE)
2	1.75 – 2.49	Disagree (D)	Moderate Extent (ME)
1	1.00 – 1.74	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Low Extent (LE)

Table 2.5 displays the involvement of Non-Catholic students in the Catholic school environments regarding spiritual.

Among the five indicators examined, the highest-rated statement—*"I feel that the spiritual teachings in the school are presented in a way that is respectful to all students"* (mean

score of 3.12)—highlights the positive perception of non-Catholic students regarding the inclusivity of religious education. This finding means that Catholic schools have successfully cultivated an environment where spiritual teachings are not imposed but instead delivered in a way that respects diverse beliefs. Moreover, this aligns with Hasan (2023), who emphasizes that compassion is a key teaching across various religions, fostering an atmosphere of understanding. Similarly, Vijayakumar (2023) argues that inclusive education enhances the learning experience by ensuring that all students, regardless of religious background, feel acknowledged. As a result, the strong agreement with this statement indicates that non-Catholic students generally do not feel alienated by the religious aspects of their education, reinforcing the idea that Catholic institutions promote respect and inclusivity.

On the other hand, the lowest-rated statement—*"I feel comfortable participating in the school's spiritual or religious activities like Mass, Marian Camp, Living Rosary, and the like"* (mean score of 2.94)—suggests that while students appreciate the respectful approach to religious teachings, some may still feel hesitant about actively engaging in Catholic traditions. Although the score still leans toward agreement, it is the lowest among the indicators, highlighting that non-Catholic students may experience some level of discomfort in fully immersing themselves in religious activities. In support of this, Smith (2021) assert that inclusivity in education should extend beyond the curriculum to include school activities, ensuring that all students feel equally involved. Furthermore, Phukan (2023) highlights that fostering a sense of interconnectedness is important in educational settings, as it helps students develop a holistic perspective on diversity. Given this, the lower rating may reflect an underlying sense of otherness that some non-Catholic students experience when engaging in faith-based school events, suggesting that additional measures could be taken to make these activities more inclusive or optional.

Additionally, the assessment highlights how students' experiences with inclusivity may evolve over time. As student's progress through different grade levels, they may become more aware of the differences between their personal beliefs and the religious traditions emphasized in school activities. According to White (2023), Catholic schools, by their nature, integrate religious practices into daily routines, which may lead non-Catholic students to feel a subtle distinction between their personal beliefs and the dominant religious framework of the school. Consequently, older students, having more exposure to these activities, may develop stronger opinions about their level of comfort in participation.

Despite these concerns, the general average score of 3.12 imply that non-Catholic students perceive Catholic schools as largely inclusive, particularly in the way spiritual teachings are delivered. While enhancement is present in ensuring that religious activities feel more welcoming to all students, the overall findings indicate that Catholic schools have successfully fostered a respectful and supportive environment. In conclusion, non-Catholic students feel that spiritual teachings are presented in a respectful manner, though some may still experience a degree of discomfort in actively participating in religious events.

Table 2.6 Summary Table on the Involvement of Non-Catholic Students in the Catholic School Environment

Indicators	M	SD	VI	I
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Pedagogical	2.97	0.91	A	GE
Social	3.04	0.93	A	GE
Psychological	2.96	0.88	A	GE
Cultural	2.98	0.89	A	GE
Spiritual	3.02	0.91	A	GE
Overall Average	2.99	0.90	A	GE

Scale	Interval	Verbal Response	Qualitative Interpretation
4	3.25 – 4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very Great Extent (VCE)
3	2.50 – 3.24	Agree (A)	Great Extent (GE)
2	1.75 – 2.49	Disagree (D)	Moderate Extent (ME)
1	1.00 – 1.74	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Low Extent (LE)

The results in Table 2.6 highlight the involvement of non-Catholic students in the Catholic School environment across five dimensions: pedagogical, social, psychological, cultural, and spiritual. The overall average mean score of 2.99, with a standard deviation of 0.90, reflects an "Agree" (A) response and is qualitatively described as "Great Extent" (GE), suggesting that, on the whole, non-Catholic students feel positively involved in these areas.

Among the five indicators, the social aspect received the highest mean score of 3.04 (standard deviation of 0.93). This indicates that non-Catholic students generally experience positive interactions and friendships, particularly within the Catholic community, fostering a supportive and connected social atmosphere. This shows that students, regardless of their faith, are able to integrate well and form meaningful relationships. Mikhael et al. (2020) emphasize the importance of interfaith dialogue in promoting mutual understanding and relationships between students from different faiths. By encouraging such dialogue, the school facilitates positive interactions and fosters a sense of community where all students, regardless of religious affiliation, feel included and supported. Pope (2021) also highlights that peer groups play a significant role in shaping students' prosocial development, which aligns with the finding that non-Catholic students are able to form strong social connections in the Catholic school environments.

In contrast, the psychological indicator received the lowest mean of 2.96 (standard deviation of 0.88), pointing to the fact that while students do feel psychologically safe and supported, additional efforts may be needed to further ensure that students from diverse religious backgrounds feel truly respected and included by the institution's policies and practices. This implies that while the school promotes an inclusive psychological environment, there may be areas where students from minority faiths or cultures feel less fully integrated into the institution's approach. Goldberg (2023) argues that interfaith education has the potential to reduce prejudices and foster psychological safety, particularly by acknowledging interreligious similarities. However, Optimal Distinctiveness Theory (Goldberg, 2023) suggests that focusing too much on commonalities could risk overshadowing the distinct identities of minority faiths, highlighting the need for a more balanced and inclusive approach to psychological safety.

In summary, the insights put forward to that while the Catholic school has succeeded in fostering a positive and inclusive social environment for non-Catholic students, there is an

opportunity to strengthen policies and initiatives that promote psychological safety and support intercultural and interfaith collaboration. Ensuring that all students, regardless of their religious background, feel equally respected and valued would further enhance the school environment. As Kaufman (2020) points out, the development of spiritual well-being is crucial for students' overall psychological health. Integrating spiritual and psychological support into school policies could help address the challenges faced by students from diverse religious backgrounds and contribute to their overall well-being.

Table 3. Significant Difference in the Involvement of Non-Catholic Student in the Catholic School Environment when they are grouped according to their Profile.

Profile	Factors	Co-efficient	P-Value	Decision	Interpretation
Sex	Pedagogical	0.077	0.93	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
	Social	-0.074	0.941	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
	Psychological	-0.646	0.520	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
	Cultural	-0.486	0.628	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
	Spiritual	-1.662	0.099	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
Grade Level	Pedagogical	-0.648	0.518	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
	Social	-1.573	0.119	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
	Psychological	-2.212	0.029	Reject Ho	Significant
	Cultural	-1.370	0.174	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
	Spiritual	-1.687	0.095	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
Religious	Pedagogical	14.100	0.590	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
Affiliation	Social	20.900	0.184	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant

Strand	Psychological	18.200	0.314	reject Ho	Significant
				Do not	Not
	Cultural	24.400	0.081	reject Ho	Significant
				Do not	Not
	Spiritual	16.700	0.406	reject Ho	Significant
				Do not	Not
	Pedagogical	2.290	0.515	Reject Ho	Significant
				Do not	Not
	Social	2.210	0.529	reject Ho	Significant
				Do not	Not
	Psychological	3.230	0.358	Do not	Not
				reject Ho	Significant
	Cultural	3.610	0.307	Do not	Not
				reject Ho	Significant
	Spiritual	4.060	0.255	Do not	Not
				Reject Ho	Significant

P-value < 0.05 = Reject Ho

Table 3 presents significant differences in the involvement of non-Catholic students in the Catholic school environment across various aspects, including pedagogical, social, psychological, cultural, and spiritual, when grouped according to their profile, such as sex, grade level, religious affiliation, and strand.

The results indicate that there are no significant differences in the involvement of non-Catholic students in the Catholic school environment across various dimensions, including pedagogical ($p = 0.939$), social ($p = 0.941$), psychological ($p = 0.520$), cultural ($p = 0.628$), and spiritual ($p = 0.099$), based on sex. Since the respective p-values exceed the 0.05 significance threshold, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This suggests that the involvement of non-Catholic students in these areas, regardless of their sex, is similarly influenced by factors other than gender. In other words, whether male or female, non-Catholic students' participation in the Catholic school environment—spanning academics, social interactions, psychological engagement, cultural involvement, and spiritual development—is primarily shaped by shared values and goals rather than their sex.

Supporting this notion, Hickey (2019) reveals that both Catholic and non-Catholic parents value similar factors, such as strong academic programs and an emphasis on moral and spiritual values, when selecting Catholic schools. This indicates that non-Catholic students, irrespective of gender, are driven by the same educational and ethical priorities. Therefore, the lack of significant differences in involvement based on sex can be attributed to the fact that their experiences are shaped more by these shared values than by gender-specific factors. Additionally, the data reveals no significant differences in the involvement of non-Catholic students in the Catholic school environment across the pedagogical ($p = 0.518$), social ($p = 0.119$), cultural ($p = 0.174$), and spiritual ($p = 0.095$) dimensions based on grade level, as the p-values exceed the 0.05 significance threshold. This indicates that grade level does not

significantly affect non-Catholic students' engagement in these areas. Despite potential variation in academic or developmental stages across grade levels, these results suggest that grade level does not play a decisive role in shaping non-Catholic students' involvement in the Catholic school environment.

This observation is in line with the perspective outlined by Duke (2020), who argues that factors such as a child's social development and emotional maturity are more influential in shaping interactions between Catholic and non-Catholic students. While grade level may reflect age, it does not appear to significantly affect involvement in the Catholic school environment. Instead, it is the individual development and emotional maturity of students that shape their engagement. Furthermore, Rutter and Smith (2020) support this view by showing that younger students tend to be more adaptable and open to new systems compared to their older counterparts. This suggests that developmental factors, rather than grade level alone, significantly influence engagement in the school setting. Therefore, while grade level itself does not exhibit a significant effect, age, emotional maturity, and developmental stage are more likely to determine non-Catholic students' interactions and experiences in Catholic schools.

On the other hand, significant differences were observed in the involvement of non-Catholic students in the Catholic school environment in terms of psychological engagement ($p = 0.029$) based on grade level. Since the computed p -value is lower than the expected significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. This finding indicates that grade level plays a significant role in shaping non-Catholic students' psychological involvement in the Catholic school environment. As student's progress through their education, their psychological experiences and perceptions are influenced by their academic and developmental stages.

This finding aligns with Duke's (2020) research, which emphasizes that emotional maturity and social development are key factors in shaping how students engage with their peers and school environment. Duke asserts that younger students tend to be more open and adaptable in their interactions, suggesting that grade level can indeed influence psychological engagement. In addition, Rutter and Smith (2020) found that younger students are more willing to adopt and utilize systems, which may explain the psychological differences observed in this study. Thus, the results suggest that grade level, which is often associated with age and developmental stage, plays a significant role in the psychological engagement of non-Catholic students in the Catholic school environment.

Furthermore, there are no significant differences in the involvement of non-Catholic students in the Catholic school environment across pedagogical ($p = 0.590$), social ($p = 0.184$), psychological ($p = 0.314$), cultural ($p = 0.081$), and spiritual ($p = 0.404$) aspects based on their religious affiliation. Since the computed p -values are all higher than the expected significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This suggests that religious affiliation does not significantly affect the involvement of non-Catholic students in these areas of the Catholic school environment.

Therefore, this aligns with Donlevy (2018), who argues that non-Catholic students' experiences in Catholic schools are not solely shaped by their religious identity. Instead, factors such as shared educational and ethical values play a significant role in determining how these students engage with the school environment. The study supports the notion that, despite their

different religious backgrounds, non-Catholic students are often influenced by common academic and moral priorities that are valued by both Catholic and non-Catholic students alike. Additionally, Hickey (2019) suggests that the appeal of Catholic schools extends beyond religious affiliation, emphasizing the strong academic programs and the schools' focus on moral and spiritual values. These findings suggest that religious affiliation, while an important identity factor, does not create significant barriers to non-Catholic students' involvement in the Catholic school environment, as shared educational goals and values serve to unify students regardless of their religious background.

Lastly, no significant differences were found in the involvement of non-Catholic students in the Catholic school environment based on their academic strand ($p = 0.515$ for pedagogical, $p = 0.529$ for social, $p = 0.358$ for psychological, $p = 0.307$ for cultural, and $p = 0.255$ for spiritual). As the respective computed p -values are all higher than the 0.05 significance threshold, this leads to the failure to reject the null hypothesis. This suggests that the strand in which non-Catholic students are enrolled does not significantly impact their involvement in these areas within the Catholic school environment.

In connection with that, this observation is supported by Rutter and Smith (2020), who found that while age and other factors influence students' willingness to engage with new systems, their involvement in school-related activities is often more influenced by personal development and maturity rather than the academic track or strand they belong to. In a similar vein, Duke (2020) highlights that factors like social development and emotional maturity have a greater influence on interactions in the school environment, which may explain why strand differences are not significantly affecting non-Catholic students' engagement across these dimensions. Thus, it can be inferred that students' involvement in the Catholic school environment is shaped by broader developmental and personal factors, rather than being significantly impacted by their academic strand.

VI. Conclusion

Non-Catholic students generally report a positive and supportive experience in Catholic schools, particularly in the pedagogical, social, and spiritual dimensions. However, there is a need for greater attention to the integration and recognition of their diverse cultural and religious backgrounds within the curriculum. While Grade 12 students demonstrated slightly higher psychological engagement, no significant differences were found based on gender, religious affiliation, or academic strand. Therefore, refining teaching practices and policies to better support the active participation of non-Catholic students could promote greater inclusivity. Ultimately, these adjustments would contribute to a more inclusive and engaging educational environment for all students.

VII. Recommendation

The following recommendations are based on the conclusion of the study:

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1. *Parents and Families.* Parents can support their children's emotional development by creating a nurturing environment that promotes open communication and emotional regulation. Encouraging active participation in school activities can also help students engage more with their community and improve their psychological well-being.
2. *Students.* Students can seek support from counselors, teachers, or peers if they face emotional challenges, especially those in Grade 11 who may experience lower psychological engagement. Engaging with peers from diverse backgrounds—academically, socially, and culturally—can promote psychological safety and foster a greater sense of belonging in the school environment.
3. *Teachers.* Teachers can contribute to a psychologically safe environment by fostering open discussions, actively listening to students' concerns, and ensuring all students feel heard and valued. Incorporating emotional literacy into lessons can help students build self-awareness and empathy. Providing targeted psychological support to Grade 11 students could address their lower psychological engagement.
4. *School Administrator.* Administrators can implement inclusive policies that promote mental well-being for all students, especially those from diverse backgrounds. Enhancing emotional and psychological support systems, such as counseling services and peer mentoring, can further assist students in their school engagement. Facilitating cross-grade collaboration between Grade 11 and Grade 12 students can also help bridge psychological engagement gaps.
5. *Future Researchers.* Future research can explore the long-term impact of attending a Catholic school on non-Catholic students' psychological and social development. Studies can also examine how these students interact with school policies on diversity and assess the effectiveness of strategies aimed at improving inclusivity for students from different religious backgrounds.

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